

Re-Examining Science and Biology Literacy for Curriculum Design and Effective Instruction

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Abstract

This paper re-examines science and biology literacy for curriculum design and effective instruction. It aims to prepare learners with up-to-date knowledge of the science area familiarize them with the autonomous characteristics of biology equip them with a working knowledge about biology literacy. The goal is to help students make decisions by using knowledge, skills and attitudes acquired through biology literacy to solve real-world problems. The aims and objectives of biology as well as good health habit to maintain good health was also emphasized. It was concluded that everyone needs the knowledge of Biology to maintain good health, happiness and survival. It was recommended that, to improve students' performance in biology, science and biology literacy must be given a wide priority in curriculum settings by the curriculum planner. Government and professional bodies such as STAN, NTI, NUT, etc. should organize in-service and re-training programmes for science teachers on effective re-examining science and biology literacy for curriculum design and effective instruction among others.

Keywords; Concepts, Science Literacy, Biology Literacy

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Introduction

Science holds a unique position among all aspects of school curriculum because it offers countless opportunities for the students. It also helps in nations' development. The aim of science education is to bring about more scientifically literate citizenry and to develop more man power to meet up with the global advancement in science and scientific literacy which has emerged as a common aim of school science curricula, but debates about the term's meaning persists (Roberts 2007); agreement among researchers in the field described its importance in developing responsible future decision – makers and encourages sustainability development (Mansfield and Reiss, 2020) in societies, which shows that scientific literacy has been acknowledge as one of the central aims of science education since, its inception, extending beyond its fundamental meaning (Guerrero and Betzate, 2021). Biology is not a single endpoint that can be attained within one biology course but is a continuum over which a person understands develop throughout their life. The importance of understanding and developing scientific literacy, particularly in biology towards science are relevant aspect of society (Bello, 2017). Citizen who are able to make informal decisions make them not just for individual benefit but also in light of their role in the more significant global economic marketplace and impacting the development of nations (Alexander and Choi 2015; Mansfield and Riss,(2020). From this perspective, it can be seen from the literarue that cultural and political integration is essential to have a democratic society; increasingly scientifically literate people could address more complex and demanding tasks more effectively and productivity.

The American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS, 2009) submitted that scientific literacy involves three principal components of nature of science: which is the scientific worldview, the scientific methods of inquiry and the nature of scientific enterprise. All these emphasize students' abilities to make use of scientific knowledge, skills and ethics or attitudes in real world situation. Scientific literacy is taken to mean that everyone should have a working knowledge of science and its role in society. Science literacy will therefore make a society to be scientifically cultured, hence such problems associated with low science culture such as poverty, low technology, pollution, population problem, environmental problem, management of resources and a host of others would be reduced to minimum. The literacy makes someone to be a better person, it helps to approach problems and issues in an unbiased perspective to observed and rationalize thought before making an informed decision. It also helps to equip oneself with tools to interpret events or happenings, brings about developments and new innovations and makes a better judgment and decisions.

Biology as one of science subjects has its' own unique characteristics that makes it distinct from all other science subjects such as chemistry and physics. Biology literacy is a sub-set of science literacy. It is expedient for everyone to be biologically literate. Biology deals with the study of living things and the interaction with their environment. Biological Science Curriculum study (BSCS, 1993) submitted that biology literacy is a lifelong, continuous endeavor. People do not attain literacy in biology or any other subject and then stop learning; rather, individuals should continue in building upon the knowledge understanding and skills that have been acquired through

time. Thus, scientists hope that students will use the knowledge and skills they obtain in biology classes to develop their literacy throughout their lives.

Biological Science Curriculum Study (BSCS, 1993) proposed, model that includes four distinct levels of biology literacy which are: Nominal, functional structural and multidimensional, at nominal level, students are literate in name only, that is they recognize the domain of biology and certain words as belonging to the realm of biology but they are not able to define or describe the word. At functional level, students are able to define certain biological terms or concepts but have limited understanding of or personal experience with them. In 2018, BSCS changed its name to Biological Science Curriculum Study Science Learning (BSCSL) which is an educational centre that develops curricular materials, provides education support, and conducts research and evaluation on the fields of science and technology.

At structural level, students understand the subject well enough to explain it to another person in their own words. Understanding how the information was obtained, ability to apply information about the subject to novel situations, known and appreciate the significance of the information to biology and to one another. At multi-dimensional level students reach a fuller understanding of biological science and its connection to other subjects and disciplines, know the history and the nature of biology, and understand interaction between biology and society. Uno and Bybee, (1994) in understanding the dimension of biology literacy opined that it is essential for biological literate students to know and understand the characteristics of scientific knowledge, the values of science and the methods and processes of scientific inquiry.

Autonomous characteristics of Biology.

Mayr, (2004) identified the following as autonomous characteristics of biology:

- i. The complexity of living system – living things unpredictable and may be difficult to study under ideal scientific conditions.
- ii. Evolutionary biology is an historical science the concepts of evolution may give rise to certain unpredictable variations that serves as threats to certain scientific theories and laws.
- iii. Change is important in biology, for example, the concepts of genetics and cell division rely on the phenomenon of change. This explains the fact that no two individuals are exactly genetically the same. Unlike other fields of science, physics or chemistry.
- iv. Biology is concerned with the living world. It is unique among the sciences, so, people need to be literate in biology because it is not all the principles that are applicable in chemistry, physics that are applicable in biology.

Principles of physical science

Bello, (2017) itemized the following principles of physical sciences that are not applicable to biology.

- i. Essentialism / typology – believes that every number of a class is said to be identical to each other, unchanging and distinctly different from member of any other class. Therefore the principle of essentialism or typology does not recognize variation.

- ii. Determinism – refers to a belief or thinking framework that whatever you do as well and whatever happens to you are caused by things that you cannot control. It implies that absolute prediction is possible. This belief does not recognize variations or those events can occur by chance.
- iii. Reductionism – reduction of complex phenomena to their smallest unit is practiced in physical sciences but in biology, the important thing to do is to learn the nature of the interactions among the components part of a complex system.
- iv. Laws – all the physical sciences theories are based on natural laws, but only few theories in biology are based on natural laws that normally have no exceptions. Biology laws are mostly based on concepts.

Nature of science

According to Abimbola and Omosewo, (2017), biology is a nature science which is composed of three components, namely: products, process and ethics. The products component is made of scientific knowledge inform-of concepts, facts, principles, laws, rules and theories. The process constitutes the various methods employed by scientists to investigate natural phenomena and events the ethical component of sciences refers to the moral rules, attitudes and principles of behavior that regulate the activities of the scientific community. A biology literate 'individual should therefore understand biological principles and the major concepts of biology, the impact of humans on the biosphere, the processes of scientific inquiry and the historical development of biological concepts.

The individual should develop personal values regarding scientific investigations biodiversity and cultural diversity, the impact of biology and biotechnology and society and the importance of biology to the individual. Also, individuals should be able to think creatively, formulate questions about nature, reason logically and critically, evaluate information, use biological technologies appropriately, make personal and ethical decisions related to biological issues and apply biological knowledge to solve problems.

Biology literacy for curriculum design and effective instruction

Biology literacy is needed in Nigeria being one of the developing countries of the world where citizens are called upon to make decisions involving curriculum development .and implementation, the environment, society, the economy, national defense and population control. International Council-for science (2011) submitted that biology knowledge can lead to improvement in many spheres of society including social, economic, political and cultural life. As a result of this, the importance of biology literacy cannot be ruled out. Koksai, (2010) define biology literacy as an educational aim that includes having 'working knowledge about biology' and making informed decision by using biology, knowledge applying them into daily life situations and knowing nature of biology. (Akintola, 2017) submitted that a biology literate person should regard controversies in areas such as agriculture, pollution, conservation or medicine as something one need to sufficiently understand in order to make informed decisions about such as; whether to

apply fertilizers to crops whether to site industries near residential areas and whether to support abortion or mass killings.

Biology is made up of topics and concepts which would bring about human good health and happiness. Human beings need the knowledge of Biology to maintain good health, safe shelter and environment to be able to pursue their goals in life (Soyibo, Ekpunobi, Akinade & Tureta, 2013). This assertion is in agreement with Akintola (2017), who submitted that biology as the study of living things is a subject that provides part of the literacy needed for national development. Biology deals with the study of living things, while chemistry and physics deals with the nature and properties of energy and non-living matter. A biology literate person should understand the nature of biology shared from other sciences and its characteristics which distinguishes it from other physical sciences.

Acquisition of Biological Attitudes, Skills and Knowledge

According to Miller (2011) biology literacy deals with acquisition of biological attitudes, skills and knowledge that allow people to participate in biological debates and develop problem-solving skill and decision-making skills in their everyday lives. This definition is in line with the aims and objectives of the new Senior Secondary School Biology Curriculum (2009), therefore the framework of working the concepts of biology literacy, were based on this definition. The aims and objectives of the New Senior Secondary School Biology Curriculum (2009) are:

- i. To prepare students to acquire adequate laboratory and field skills in biology
- ii. Meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology
- iii. Ability to apply scientific knowledge to everyday life in matter of personal and community health and agriculture
- iv. Reasonable and functional scientific attitudes.

Application of Science and Biology Literacy to Life

It is expected that students should be able to make connections between what they learn at school and how it can be applied to their everyday life. This is in support of Kwesigabo, Mwangi, Kakoko and Killewo (2012) that prevention and control of health problems sometimes requires interventions beyond health sector programme and initiatives. They submitted that public education is needed and that schools need to play a role in educating young people about human biology so that a greater understanding of individual and community health can be fostered. According to Soyibo, Ekpunobi, Akinade and Tureta (2013), infectious diseases contribute greatly towards the poor health of people in the world all over, particularly in developing countries. To move towards better health, the disease-causing microorganisms have to be controlled. In an attempt to control these harmful micro-organisms, vectors and the maintenance of good health, students need to be exposed to one of the topics taught in Biology titled "Towards Better Health right from the Senior Secondary School One (S.S. I) in Nigeria.

Under the control of harmful micro-organisms, students are exposed to various methods of preventing and controlling the spread of the micro-organisms such as sterilization, use of antibiotics, high salinity and dehydration methods. Sterilization method kills or removes all micro-organism through the application of high temperature which destroys pathogenic microorganisms in food by cooking the food properly. Antiseptics such as alcohol (70%) boric acid, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), potassium tetra-oxo-manganate VII ($KMnO_4$) are used on cuts, abrasions and wounds on our skins to prevent infection by inhibiting microbial growth. Also, antibiotics such as penicillin are used to control diseases caused by pathogenic bacteria.

High salinity inhibits the growth of the microbial cell and so prevents its multiplication. Therefore, washing cuts and wounds with salt solution prevent them from becoming infected. Foods are preserved by dehydration methods such as drying; drying in the sun prevents microbial growth and subsequently kills disease-causing micro-organism. The knowledge of the habit and life cycle of vectors taught in Biology help us to control their activities. Vectors are insects or animals such as houseflies, mosquitoes, lice, rodents' e.g. rats and mice that transmit disease-causing organisms or carry a particular disease from one living thing to another. According to Olufemi, (2016) as reported in the daily newspaper Punch Friday, January 15, 2016 Lassa fever is ravaging in Nigeria again.

According to the report, the affected states cut across the Northern and Southern, parts of the country and as the time of this report 41 people have been reported dead of the Lassa fever out of 86 cases of infection in the ten states across the country. The virus that causes Lassa fever was identified in 1969 in a town called Lassa in the present-day Borno State. Since then, the disease, is seen as endemic in West Africa, has been killing thousands of people every year. World Health Organization reported that between 300,000 and 500,000 persons come down with Lassa fever annually, out of which 5,000 deaths are recorded. It was then submitted that with adequate awareness of the causes of the disease, it is easy to reduce the rate of infection and that what is needed is personal-hygiene and proper sanitation around the home environment to combat the infection from the vector of the Lassa fever which are the rodents such as rat.

Houseflies spread the micro-organisms that cause diseases like typhoid, cholera, dysentery and poliomyelitis. Mosquitoes spread diseases like malaria, yellow fever, dengue, encephalitis and filariasis. Rat, fleas and lice transmit diseases such as plague and typhus the knowledge of various diseases transmit by these vectors will help in preventing them from having contact with people in order to maintain good health. Good health, according to the World Health Organization is defined as a state of physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of diseases or infirmity to maintain good health the following must be taking into practice:

- i. Eating of a balanced diet
- ii. Exercising the body
- iii. Resting
- iv. Avoiding smoking, drinking of alcohol, eating of junk foods and drug addiction.
- v. Taking of preventive measures through vaccination against diseases.

vi. Cleanliness and care of the body

Eating of a balanced diet - Balance diet, according to Soyibo, Ekpunobi, Alcinade, Tureta, (2013) is the appropriate types and amounts of food substances the human body needs to perform optimally. It is what the body needs for the supply of nutrition and energy for maintaining body cells, tissues and organs and for supporting proper growth and development. In line with this, Extension America's Research-based Learning Network, (2009) submitted that: with better nutrition students are better able to learn, students have fewer absences, and students' behavior improves, causing fewer disruptions in the classroom. Awareness of the above facts would make the students and parents cultivate the habit of good feeding. Juma,(2015) discovered that the food taboo practices mentioned by both teachers and students indicated that education about the importance of eating a balanced diet is needed in some communities as it was found out that some participants mentioned food taboos such as pregnant women do not eat nutritious food like eggs for fear of delivering babies without hair.

Under the cleanliness and care of the body taught in senior school biology curriculum, students are exposed to the precautions to be taken to avoid being infected such as: keeping oneself and belongings clean.

- i. Washing of hands before eating and after eating and using of the toilet
- ii. Covering of food
- iii. Drinking of clean water regularly
- iv. Wearing of shoes and washing of stockings after use
- v. Staying away from people with infectious disease
- vi. Sleeping under a mosquito-treated net
- vii. Keeping the house and surrounding clean.

According to World Health Organization, WHO, (2023) lack of awareness of personal hygiene leads to health problems in order to prevent health problems, students are taught the precautions to prevent the spread of infection such as:

- i. Washing of hands before preparing or serving food.
- ii. Washing of used plates always
- iii. Always cough, sneeze and blow your nose into a handkerchief or tissue
- iv. Do not spit on the floor but into a handkerchief, tissue or wash basin
- v. Always use a latrine when urinating or defecating and wash your hands afterwards
- vi. Throw all rubbish into covered bins for disposal
- vii. Stay away from public places when you have an infectious disease.

From the above points of view, it is clearly seen that everyone needs the knowledge of Biology to maintain good health, happiness and survival. Moreover, Ingraham, (2004) submitted that people generally don't know even what they are made of or the basic conditions that need to exist for healing. He emphasized the power of Biology literacy as it helps to know how our body works. He further stressed that biology literacy is as important as other basic academic needs. It will help people to learn, remember and make use of other information about their body from any other source for the rest of their lives. In Nigeria, Senior Secondary Biology curriculum especially

at the S.S 2 class exposes students to the various systems of the body such as Reproductive system, Digestive system, circulatory system, excretory system, nervous system, respiratory system and skeletal system. All these will help people to know everything about how their bodies work. For an example the knowledge of people in reproductive system helps in family planning to have the number of the children they can care for. It also helps in controlling the human population thereby preventing overcrowding which may result in food shortage, limited space, health problems and environmental degradation. People can achieve social -well-being through a well-balanced family and community life.

In counseling, genetics counseling is now available in marriage, the blood of prospective couples is analyzed to detect those who have genes of certain hereditary diseases and advise them on the chances of their children having such diseases such as haemophilia. Rhesus factor and sickle-cell anemia. This is aimed at reducing incidence of these sex-linked hereditary diseases (Rustaman & Hall, 2012). This is also one of the vital points why every student must be literate in Biology at the senior secondary schools; all the students of Biology are exposed to all these facts that will make them to make a right choice in marriage and to live a happy life for the rest of their lives. Through practical biology certain scientific attitudes and skills that are vital to life are build up in students such as the power of careful observation, perseverance, carefulness, honesty, open-mindedness etc. which would help student to live successfully in life. This biology literacy is reviewed to expose the importance of Biology to every human being and to educate the populace on the significance of biology literacy so as to help them in making informed decision by using the knowledge, skills and attitudes in biology to solve human problems and to improve student knowledge of biology and enhance their better performance.

Conclusion

The right selection and appropriate use of re-examining science and biology literacy for curriculum design and effective instruction may result into better achievement and favorable attitude and skills in the part of the learners.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made: -

- i. In order to improve students' performance in science and biology literacy must be given a wide priority setting by the curriculum planner.
- ii. Government and professional bodies such as STAN, NTI, NUT, etc. should organize in-service and re-training programmes for science and biology literacy for curriculum design and effective instruction.
- iii. Government should develop a manual on science and biology literacy and train teachers on it through the Ministry of Education.
- iv. Students should be allowed to use their skills with all instructional resources in biology classroom instruction in order for students to yield positive attitude towards the subject.

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